

HOW TO TRANSLATE AN IDIOM IN UZBEK LANGUAGE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6948646>

Abstract. *Translating idioms is challenging for translators due to the cultural differences between a source language and a target language. In this regard, this research aimed how to translated idioms in Uzbek language.*

Keywords: *idiomatic expressions, equivalence, understanding meaning, phrases, target language, source language.*

КАК ПЕРЕВЕСТИ ИДИОМУ НА УЗБЕКСКИЙ ЯЗЫК

Аннотация. *Перевод идиом является сложной задачей для переводчиков из-за культурных различий между исходным и целевым языками. В связи с этим данное исследование было направлено на перевод идиом на узбекский язык.*

Ключевые слова: *идиоматические выражения, эквивалентность, понимание значения, словосочетания, язык перевода, исходный язык.*

INTRODUCTION

What exactly are idioms?

An idiom is widely used expressing your thinking which contains figurative meaning that is different from real meaning.

For example: „sweet tooth”

It describes people who really love sweet foods, in figurative meaning.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Translating idiomatic expressions represents a real challenge to students, especially when translation occurs between two distinct languages like English and Uzbek which are linguistically and culturally different. Because translating idiomatic expressions may show a significant misunderstanding and mistranslation of the source text and because it is not easy to translate an idiomatic expression or to find an equivalent one to that of the source language.

RESULTS

Equivalence/Reformulation

This allows to preserve the meaning of an idiom or proverb by finding a target language equivalent.

Understand the meaning of the idiom or sentence (or even paragraph in certain cases) and come up with idiom that expresses the same meaning in the target language. This is the method applied by professional translators and it is what allows professional translators to create texts that read like they have been written in the target language, rather than as translations.

1. Step: Identity idiom

“You have tomatoes on your eyes”.

2. Step: Understanding idiom

The meaning of idioms should never be understood literally. That is to say the translator must first analyze what the writer has intended to say before s/he can even think of translating the expression.

What it means: “You are not seeing what everyone else can see. It refers to real objects, though - not abstract meanings”.

3. Step: Find an equivalent idiom in the target language.

“Ko’zini yog’ bosgan”.

DISCUSSION

By using this strategy, the translator tries to find an idiom in the target language, which is equivalent to that of the source language both in terms of meaning and lexical items. Such a strategy is very difficult to be achieved, because each language has its own way and devices to express certain concepts, which differ radically from another. However, it is regarded as the ideal strategy for translating idioms.

CONCLUSIONS

Therefore, the most important issue in translating idioms is the ability to distinguish the difference between the literal meaning and the real meaning of the expression. This is why recognizing and being able to use idioms appropriately requires excellent command over the source language. Larson (1984) believed that the real danger comes from translating an idiom literally, since the translated idiom will be nonsense in the receptor language. Here a some examples that translated by using this translation method - finding equivalence

English	Uzbek
the grass is always greener on the other side	Oldingdan oqqan suvni qadri yo’q
To feel blue	Tushkun ahvoldga tushmoq
To see red	Tepa sochi tikka bo’lmoq
Every cloud has a silver line	Oyning o’n beshi yorug’ , o’n beshi qorong’u
Red hot	qaynoq , yorqin
It is not cup of my tea	Bu meni didimga tug’ri kelmaydi

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